

Biological studies of *Cuminum cyminum* plant on antibiotic resistant bacteria

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ABSTRACT— The study was carried out to assess the quantity of plants, *Cuminum cyminum* for their microbial effects. The extracts were screened for their biological activities against bacterial pathogens including *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. Results showed that inhibition zone and MIC for *Cuminum cyminum* seed and leaves the inhibition zone and MIC in all extract It was resistant to bacteria. However the antimicrobial activity of leaves and seeds *Cuminum cyminum* and extracts was higher than that of antibiotic used against the tested microorganisms.

Keywords— *Cuminum cyminum*, Antibacterial activity and antibiotic

1. INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants have been used in folk medicine in Libyan rural areas at relatively cheaper expenses than modern medicine. They have been widely used as produce several secondary metabolites like phenols, flavonoids, quinones, tannins, alkaloids, saponins, and sterols which are important sources of biocides and many other pharmaceutical drugs (Naili *et al.*, 2010). Medicinal plants are important in pharmacological research and drug development (Li and Vederas, 2009). Plants have been a rich source of medicines because they produce wide array of bioactive molecules,

Most of which probably evolved as chemical defense against predation or infection and antioxidant compounds (Cosimir and Min, 2008).

Many plants possess antimicrobial activities and are used for the treatment of different activities and are used for the treatment of different diseases (Arora and Kaur, 1999).

Cuminum cyminum is a native of arid soils. It is commonly found in Saudi Arabia, Syria, Jordan, Egypt, Iran, India and Pakistan. It is commonly known as Hanzal, Indrian, Tumma or Bitter apple. It is a large creeping herb, with deeply dissected lobulate leaves Flowers, solitary, monoecious of yellow colour. Fruits rounded 7-9cm in diameter, green and white, striped become yellow when ripe (Jafri, 1966).

The *Cuminum cyminum* is useful against fever, intestinal parasites, hepatic and abdominal diseases, visceral and cerebral congestions. Fruit juice with sugar is a house hold remedy in dropsy (Anonymous, 1970). Seeds are diuretic (Vohora and Khan, 1981). Fruits are used against tumors of gastrointestinal tract. It is more pronouncedly used in anticancerous drug. It is effective in leukemia and joint pains. *Cuminum cyminum* is widely used by rural inhabitants as a purgative, anti-diabetic, anti-neoplastic, anti-rheumatic, and anti-allergic agent (Tannin-Spitz *et al.*, 2007). They are found mainly in plants belonging to the Cucurbitaceae family, but have also been found in several other families of the plant kingdom (Tannin-Spitz *et al.*, 2007). Although, the whole fruit is often used for the treatment of the aforementioned diseases, but some particular parts of the fruit are also used for specific purposes.

One of such example is the traditional application of the dried pulp and seed extract of *Cuminum cyminum* for the treatment of constipation and diabetes (Kumar *et al.*, 2008; Nmila *et al.*, 2000). The use of colocynth as a drug has been documented in ancient times and religious books (Khafagi *et al.*, 2006). *Cuminum cyminum* is traditionally used as an antidiabetic medication in tropical and subtropical countries (Diwan *et al.*, 2000).

Nowday, bacterial infection especially those caused multi drug resistant (MDR) Bacteria have become one of the great challenge for modern healthcare. Therefore, discovering New antibacterial compounds with improve activity is necessary. Majority of scientists define multi drug resistant to at least 3 classes of antimicrobial agents (Falagas *et al.*; 2006).

2- MATERIALS AND METHODS

leaves and Seeds of selected plant were separated and washed with distilled water several times, then dried in open air (Figures 1). Its height is 60 cm, with lobed leaves, a distinctive aroma, and its large white flowers. It gives white top fruits, with small black seeds. The plant grows wild in most areas of Libya. Fresh of *Cuminum cyminum* washed two times tap water and subjected to shade drying at room temperature the dried plant material was powdered using a mechanical grinder (Akinpelu *et al.*, 2008; Alshammary and Ibrahim, 2014). The powdered materials of *Cuminum cyminum* were extracted with methanol 10 grams of each plant powders were added to 100ml of methanol (80% w/v). Crude extract were evaporated at 45°C with the rotary evaporator the extracts were collected and stored at 4°C until further use (Akinpelu *et al.*, 2008; Alshammary and Ibrahim, 2014). The antimicrobial activity of the plants extracts was determined using the agar well diffusion method (Sathishkumar *et al.*, 2008), where Mueller-Hinton (MH) agar plates were seeded with bacterial strain on each plate wells were made by sterile standard cork borer. Each well was filled with 30µl of the different concentrations (0.8, 0.4, 0.2, 0.1, 0.01, 0.001, 0.0001 and 0.00001 g/ml) of studied plants extracts and the plates were then incubated for 24 - 48 h at 37°C for bacteria .

The of inhibition zones were measured, the results are presented as mean of triplicate. The minimal inhibition concentration (MIC) values were evaluated according to published procedures (Koneman *et al.*, 1997; Iscan *et al.*, 2002 and Guven *et al.*, 2005). The minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined only with micro-organisms that displayed inhibitory zones. MIC was determined by dilution of the plants extracts and pipetting 30µl of each dilution into wells dilutions of the extracts within a concentrations range of (0.8 - 0.00001 g/ml) . MIC was defined as the lowest concentration that inhibited the visible microbial growth (NCCLS, 2005).

Figure (1): *Cuminum cyminum*

2.1- Antibiotic Sensitivity Tests

In vitro antimicrobial susceptilit to four antibiotics in Table. The inoculum was prepared by adding isolated colonies of the microorganism from an overnight nutrient agar plate into 2ml try tone soya broth (TSB). A sterile cotton swab was dipped into the adjusted suspension. The swab was rotated several times and pressed firmly on the inside wall of the tube above the fluid level to remove excess inoculum from the swab. The swab was streaked over the entire surface of the sterile Mueller Hinton Agar plate. This procedure was repeated by streaking two more times, rotating the plate approximately each time to ensure an even distribution of inoculum. plates were allowed to dry for 5 minutes and then the antimicrobial disks were dispensed onto the surface of inoculated agar plates using an Oxide antibiotic. Plates were then incubated at 37°C for 18-22 hours. The diameters of the zones of inhibition are measured to the nearest mm using a venier calipers (junior) , zones diameters were interpreted as being susceptible Sensitive (S) or Resistant (R) according to (NCCLS, 2001).

Table (1) Antibiotic Sensitivity testing

Kanamycin	K	30mg/ml
Gentamicin	CN	10mg/ml
Tetracycline	TE	30mg/ml
Cefotaxime	CTX	30mg/ml

3- RESULTS

3.1 Antibacterial activity:

3.1.1 *Staphylococcus aureus*

Showed of the studied plants extract against *Streptococcus pneumoniae* . Results showed that inhibition zone and MIC for *Cuminum cyminum* seed and fruits the inhibition zone and MIC in all extract It was resistant to bacteria.

Table (2) the effect of *Cuminum cyminum* plant extract (distilled water, methanol) against the *S. aureus*.

Used Bacteria	Solvent	Plant Part	Diameter of Inhibition Zone (mm)
<i>C. cyminum</i>	Distilled Water	Leaves	9
<i>C. cyminum</i>	Methanol	Leaves	7
<i>C. cyminum</i>	Distilled Water	Seeds	10
<i>C. cyminum</i>	Methanol	Seeds	16

Figure (3): *Cuminum cyminum* seeds extract against *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Figure (4): *Cuminum cyminum* leaves extract against *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Figure (2) Antimicrobial activities of studied plant *Cuminum cyminum* extract against Bacteria.

3.1.2 *Streptococcus pneumoniae*

Table (10) showed of the studied plants extract against *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. Results showed that inhibition zone and MIC for *Cuminum cyminum* seed, while for fruits of *Cuminum cyminum*, where the inhibition zone zones of inhibition did not show any effect on the bacterial growth

Table (3) the effect of *Cuminum cyminum* plant extract (distilled water, methanol) against the *S. pneumoniae*

Used Bacteria	Solvent	Plant Part	Diameter of Inhibition Zone (mm)
<i>C. cyminum</i>	Distilled Water	Leaves	N.A
<i>C. cyminum</i>	Methanol	Leaves	20
<i>C. cyminum</i>	Distilled Water	Seeds	22
<i>C. cyminum</i>	Methanol	Seeds	N.A

Figure (5) Antimicrobial activities of studied plant *Cuminum cyminum* extract against Bacteria.

Figure (6): *Cuminum cyminum* seeds extract against *Streptococcus pneumoniae*

Figure (7): *Cuminum cyminum* leaves extract against *Streptococcus pneumoniae*

Antibiotic Sensitivity

Table show the rates of sensitivity of Gram negative and Gram positive bacteria results showed that the sensitivity pattern of *S. pneumoniae* was sensitive to K, CN, TE and CTX Figures (8). However, *S. dysenteriae* was resistant to K, CN, TE and CTX Figures (9). Antimicrobial resistance developed by microbes against antibiotics open serious debates in this issue and recognized as a serious problem by global medicinal and research community (Finch,2004).

Antibiotic	Symbol	Concentration	Organism	
			<i>S. pneumoniae</i>	<i>S. dysenteriae</i>
Kanamycin	K	30mg/ml	S	R
Gentamicin	CN	10mg/ml	S	R
Tetracycline	TE	30mg/ml	S	R
Cefotaxime	CTX	30mg/ml	S	R

Figure (8) Antibiotic sensitivity testing of *S. pneumoniae*

Figure (9) Antibiotic sensitivity testing of *S. dysenteriae*

4. DISCUSSION

If we notice that the *Cuminum cyminum* plant was a good resistance to different types of bacteria Similar results observed by (Memon et al., 2003)

5- Conclusions

The present investigation proves that antimicrobial activity of seed and leaves *Cuminum cyminum* extracts was higher than that of antibiotic used against the nsidered adequate to demonstrate that *Cuminum cyminum* extracts can be considered a good antibacterial agent, it can be used to an antibacterial overcoat against the strain that a major problem of resistance in hospitals.

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